

SOCIOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF YOUTH SLANG AND WAYS OF TRANSLATING IT FROM ENGLISH INTO RUSSIAN (BASED ON THE MATERIAL OF MAGAZINES)

*Prezident Ta'lim muassasalari Agentligi tizimidagi
Abu Ali Ibn Sino nomidagi ixtisoslashtirilgan maktabning
ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi*

Djurayeva Visola Olimjonovna

ANNOTATION The importance of our research is that youth slang is constantly evolving. American slang has been formed and developed with American history. According to the authors, Russian slang contains a large number of English borrowings. Modern slang in English represents one of the most pressing and contradictory problems in modern lexicology. This article is devoted to the examination of a concept of modern English youth slang.

Formal or casual interactions can take many different forms. The typical variety, conditions, and context of formal or official topics serve as the basis for formal language variation. One of the variants that might be heard in various groups is referred to as slang. Colloquial language refers to everyday speech (from the Latin col- "together" and loqui "to speak").

KEY WORDS Youth slang, symbol, formal language, content, sociolinguistics, Clipping, blending, borrowing, acronyms, initials.

INTRODUCTION

A variety of conversations are classified as formal or informal. Variation in formal language is typically based on the standard variety, circumstances, and context of formal or official matters. Meanwhile, informal language variation typically occurs in a variety of non-standard languages, the situation, and the context of an informal or casual matter. Conversations and interactions in society or the

community itself will generate various forms of diversity and variety of languages. It reflects the different contexts in which they use the language. Language views differ based on the person's status as a social user, gender, age, ethnicity, and the type of social networking in which he or she participates. These variations are usually caused by differences in styles, context register, and politeness. Variations occur as a result of the language situation in an informal speech context. Slang refers to one of the variations that can be found in a variety of communities. Language variation is formed by a convention or agreement among language users, and it is based on the nature of language as an arbiter. Furthermore, slang employs informal words and expressions that are not commonly used in the speaker's native language. In formal situations, most people speak carefully, but in many informal situations, a more relaxed style of speech makes a better impression. Normal conversation is referred to as colloquial (from the Latin *col-* "together" and *loqui* "to speak"). Speaking in colloquial English shows that you are a warm, friendly, and approachable person who wants to connect with other people on a personal level. e.¹ Slang is a topic that elicits strong emotions (Coleman, 2012), and it can even slang 'bitch please' elicits feelings of warmth and loyalty from the members. When uttered by people outside the group, however, it elicits hostility.

Some people adore slang and make certain that they always use the most up-to-date terms, despite the fact that said slang still exists. Others, on the other hand, despise it and look down on those who use it. When someone uses slang, it indicates that they are uneducated, stupid, or hopelessly out of date.

Slang is a special vocabulary used by any group of people of a low or disreputable character; it is a low and vulgar language (Coleman, 2012). Slang is used by a speaker to create social dynamics with the people to whom he or she is speaking. Furthermore, slang defines social spaces, and attitudes toward it aid in the identification and construction of social groups and identities (Adams, 2009).

¹ Slang Created and Used in Icak.com Site (Nico Harared)

Furthermore, there are 26 reasons why people use slang (Coleman, 2012). It is that slang can be uttered to reveal their ideas, feelings, and expressions, and it can only be understood by certain people in a specific area and may not be known by people outside the group. They use slang words as a secret code and a symbol of solidarity within groups or between groups.

The virtual world is a world that fosters conversation and intimacy among groups or communities on the Internet, where slang is developed. Slang establishes in-groups and out-groups and serves as a symbol of belonging (Coleman, 2012). The group and the community congregate at various locations, one of which is an entertainment site. Said site, such as one based on humor, is the most popular among the young generation these days. 1cak.com is a popular website in Indonesia. It is a humor-based site with image and video content, similar to 9gag.com. This website is amusing and full of things that might be considered funny, ridiculous, or realistic in everyday life.

Several posts contain images and text that combine to form a humorous slang. Unfortunately, some visitors to this site are baffled as to what the slang's function is and where it came from. In line with that, the primary reason for 1cak.com being prioritized in this study is that it contains a large number of slang words and expressions. One of the slang taken from a post in 1cak.com

Furthermore, many researchers have conducted slang analysis in specific studies. Trimastuti (2017) investigated slang words used in social media, particularly in the alay language variation. The qualitative method was used in this study, and the researcher chose descriptive techniques consideration regional diversity.

BlackBerry Messenger, Twitter, Instagram, Path, Line, and Facebook were used to collect the information. The researcher used the observation method to collect data. The researcher discovered that alay language variation is one of the slang languages used in teenage conversation. It is understandable to a certain group, particularly those who use it themselves. In Bahasa, there are many errors in the

Alay language variation for communication. However, in social media, it can be minimized to avoid misunderstandings in message delivery.

The relevance of research

Slang is widely used by people of all disciplines. American slang has been formed and developed with American history. It has unique features and functions. ... American slang sociolinguistic studies help people learn more about American culture and society. This study is concerned with the characteristics of youth slang used in modern English. The purpose of this article is to examine the use of slang expressions among the younger generation. The definition of slang begins to pique the interest of modern philology. There are now a plethora of slang definitions available, many of which contradict one another. According to the authors, Russian slang contains a large number of English borrowings. This article is devoted to the examination of a concept of modern English youth slang. The importance of our research is that youth slang is constantly evolving. As an integral part of language, modern slang in English represents one of the most pressing and contradictory problems in modern lexicology. This study promotes a solution to the problem of determining an entity and the main distinguishing characteristics of the studied phenomenon.

This study looked into the slang that was created based on word formation processes as well as its functions, as well as the social factors that influenced the existence of slang. The qualitative method was used in this study, which resulted in descriptive data. The data were gathered through the use of an observation method (screenshot) on the meme or posts that follow certain picture postings. The full observation method was then used to ensure that the researcher had no influence on the data collected. The information was gleaned from 1cak.com's 'trending' and 'legend' posts.

The relevance of research : The key characteristics of Russian youth dialects will be examined, with consideration given to linguistics, sociolinguistics, language policy, and ideology. The impact of English is significant in some versions of

Russian.

The thesis's overarching goal is to show that social dialects have just as much of a home in (Soviet) Russian as they do in any other language. These dialects have a sizable social foundation in parts. The effect of Russian criminal jargon on slang and colloquial language is undiminished.

Research objectives: The primary goal of this work is to investigate the characteristics of the usage of young slang in the media of English-speaking and Russian-speaking nations, taking into

Questions

1. What is slang, the definition of slang, the origin of this unit?
2. What is history of the origin of slang and assumptions about it?
3. What is the sociolinguistic features of youth slang in English?
4. What kind of sociolinguistic features have youth slang in Russian?
5. What is the ways of translating youth slang from English into Russian?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research focused on analyzing slang by describing its word formation processes and functions. First, it is discovered in this study that some of Yule's types of slang word formation processes are used in 1cak.com. Clipping, blending, borrowing, acronyms, initials, and derivation by adding specific affixes are all examples (suffix). Second, it is discovered that, in addition to what Coleman has proposed, there are two additional functions of slang language; that there are 26 reasons why people use slang, such as mocking and praising. Speaking Hymes theory proposes that the social factors proposed by Johnstone and Marcellino influence the appearance and existence of slang. Variations in language are caused by social and situational factors that influence the use of language.

Argot, jargons and slang have always been subjects of interest and re- search for Soviet linguists. But the research done in these fields has remained rather scanty except for the 1920s and 1930s. This state of affairs, although deplored by some

scholars, is due to a number of reasons.² Over the last few decades Soviet linguistics has been predominantly prescriptive. This is especially apparent in the areas of lexicology and lexicography. Expressions regarded as falling outside the literary language were omitted from all dictionaries, monolingual as well as multilingual. This principle, which is the product of Soviet language policy, becomes clearly noticeable in the dictionaries published in the Soviet Union since the early 1950s. Soviet language policy has a double purpose. One is prospective and aims at modification of existing linguistic norms - this is called "Language Structuring" or "Language Planning" (языковое строительство); the other is retrospective and aims at conservation - It is called "Speech Culture" or "Language Maintenance" (культура языка/культура речи),³ (in both these are as the Soviet Union has been unquestionably successful. However, the abundance of old words and of words fallen off from argot shows that modern argot is going through a crisis, a phase of transition. One can hardly speak of its complete extinction because, unfortunately, conditions for the survival of the criminal dregs of society and their language - an unavoidable consequence of the isolation from normal life - have not yet been completely eradicated

An external indication of the crisis through which thieves' cant is passing is its unprecedented wide base after being uprooted from its natural soil. [Straten (1931), p. 140]

METHODOLOGY

Comparative, descriptive, and statistical approaches might be utilized to gather and review data in this study. The collected data is analyzed and compared using the synchronic method. The research methods used to negotiate meaning through data interpretation without the belief that objective information could be derived during

² See e . g . F. P. F i l i n , "K probleme social'noj obuslovlennosti jazyka ," in: VJa, 1966, no. 4, p. 37.

³ See L. B. Nikol ' s k i j , Sinchroaaaja sociolingvistika (Teorija i pro - bierny), Moskva, 1976, p. 112, and "Jazykovaja plitika " i n : BSĒ, 3rd e d . , v o l . 30, Moskva, 1978, p. 470.

data collection; reality is a social construction with the ultimate goal of understanding what some people think and do, the obstacles they face, and how they overcome them; whether the terms and slang are commonly used in everyday speech or are only used by teenagers.

Target population: for public, specialists and non-specialists.

Equipment: books, computers, compulsory participants (scientists, lexicographers, orientalists, philologists, phonetics, historians, ethno-linguists, religious specialists), volunteer participants (political specialists, students, linguists and religious specialists), editors, publishers.

Lexicography is a complex field of linguistics, so the work requires cross-examination and proof from many experts, analytical, comparative-contrast data, especially in terms of the specific narrow scope of lexicography.

CONCLUSION

During the course of this research, an examination of the operation of the English borrowed vocabulary and its adaptation in the Russian language was carried out. The primary methods of transmitting English Youth slang into Russian media language are tracing and transliterating. Furthermore, a native Russian phrase that is part of the English language's regularly used lexicon is employed to represent a foreign notion.

The distribution of argot, jargon and slang has been discussed as well as the situations which call for the use of these varieties. The claim that speakers of the literary language (or members of the intelligentsia) must resort to the colloquial language when speaking in an unconstrained atmosphere has been proved wrong. Russian argot (феня), the Jargons and slang are far from leading a phantom existence. On the contrary, they have great vitality and considerable distribution.

Completed research and its outcomes are equally important for the linguistic and non-linguistic spheres of society in today's developed and fast-moving competitive environment. Linguistics has always been regarded as a subfield of

other sciences: it is studied in general linguistics at times, and in religious, social, and philosophical studies at other times. To solve unsolved problems in various branches of linguistics such as cognitive, socio, ethnolinguistics, and even religious literature studies, the modern approach to linguistics necessitates studying linguistics separately and thoroughly.

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